

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION, ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCE, AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTIONS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS: BASIS FOR CURRICULUM ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Business programs in higher education institutions are paramount to foster entrepreneurship as it hones students' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and desires which are essential for their success as future entrepreneurs. The study aimed at determining the students' levels of entrepreneurship education (EE), entrepreneurial competence (EC) and entrepreneurial intentions (EI) among college students who finished entrepreneurship courses at St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Dipolog City, Philippines. It also focused on measuring the association of students' levels of entrepreneurship education to their entrepreneurial competence, and entrepreneurial intentions. This study is a descriptive-correlational research design. A census approach was employed, and survey questionnaire was used to collect data from 100 college students enrolled in business programs. This study utilized both descriptive statistics to analyze the central tendency and variability of collected data, and inferential statistics to measure the relationships, differences, and patterns among variables. Findings revealed that in general, students' levels of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial intentions were high. The differences in students' level of EE was not significant when they were grouped according to their profile. Moreover, entrepreneurship education was positively and significantly correlated with entrepreneurial competence, and their relationship was high. Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions were also positively and significantly correlated however, their relationship was at a moderate level. The study suggested that entrepreneurship education be intensified through curriculum enhancement specifically on creating a more contextualized syllabus for entrepreneurship courses, highlighting hands-on experience that would greatly develop students' EC and EI leading to a successful career in business.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Competence, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Curriculum Enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

Frederick, O’Conor & Kuratko (2016) postulated that entrepreneurship is a fluid process of vision, transformation, and creation. It takes a lot of energy and passion to come up with and implement new value-added ideas and creative solutions. Its indispensable components include the desire to take calculated risks concerning time, equity, or career; the ability to put together a successful venture team; the capacity to think creatively to gather needed resources; and the power to sense opportunity where others see disorder, contradiction, and uncertainty.

Undoubtedly, entrepreneurship is the process of creating, setting up, and managing a new business in order to make money while taking on financial risk. In a broader fashion, entrepreneurship is the operation of changing the status quo by addressing the most important issues and pain points in our society, frequently through developing new products or services or opening up new markets. Opportunities for business are constant since people need goods and services to thrive.

Indeed, it is an activity of starting a firm or businesses while incurring financial risks with the expectation of a profit. It can be basically characterized as a science of transforming ideas into business venture, where the concept of business pertains to commercial endeavor engaged in as a means of livelihood. Kuckertz, Kollmann, and Stöckmann (2017) clearly describe it as the process of spotting an opportunity and effectively seizing it to create a successful business. Businesses provide economic contributions. Stoica et al. (2020) argued that a country's economic prosperity is greatly influenced by its entrepreneurial spirit. Additionally, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs are regarded as significant drivers of economic growth because of their involvement in the production of new jobs, employment possibilities, and new technologies as well as the promotion of competition, and competitiveness.

Moreover, all developed and emerging nations share a common concern about unemployment especially in light of global financial crisis, jobless rates have been rising everywhere (Taha, Ranlan & Noor, 2017). Numerous policies and techniques have been implemented globally in order to curb unemployment. In addition to other options, entrepreneurship is one of the most popular ones for the problem of unemployment (Nazri, Aroosha & Omar, 2016), and considering that entrepreneurship is viewed as a crucial driver of economic growth, innovation, and employment creation (Martinez-Rodriguez, Albiñana, F. & Albiñana, A, 2020). A lot of decision-makers worldwide actively pursue measures that will boost the number of entrepreneurs (Acs et al., 2017; Fotopoulos & Storey, 2019).

In this sense, entrepreneurship is regarded as a necessity and opportunity (Rodriguez, Albiñana, F. & Albiñana, A, 2020). People are becoming more and more interested in the possibility of starting their own businesses, whether this interest stems from a need for a source of income due to a lack of other employment options (necessity) or from an opportunity that they believe exists but has not yet been fully exploited by established businesses (opportunity) (Peña, Guerrero & Pernía, 2014).

Essentially, the role of every entrepreneur is vital in any business development. From the perspective of management, an entrepreneur is an individual who looks for opportunities, plans, gathers resources, manages, and takes on the risks of a business in order to make a constructive contribution to society (Edralin, 2016). With this in mind, an entrepreneur is a person who has an idea, tries to turn the concept into a marketable product or service, and establishes a business to help them in their endeavor. The majority of the risk and responsibility for starting a new firm is assumed by the entrepreneur, who is frequently considered as a visionary or an inventor. Everybody who has the desire to establish a business and work for oneself qualifies as an entrepreneur. This includes small business owners, content creators, startup founders, and people of all sizes.

The emerging characteristics required of an entrepreneur today include higher education, knowledge of core business operations, proficiency in information technology, values innovation for new venture, social, ecological and economic gains, ethical, transparent, and group accountability, empowerment, and the ability to make difference, among others. Several literatures revealed about the personal characteristics of entrepreneur includes among others confidence, flexibility, need to achieve, commitment, persevering, disciplined, risk-taker, problem-solver, and visionary. Many of these may be developed or acquired through instructions and learning from successful entrepreneurs who had gone ahead. It is therefore imperative to develop entrepreneurs' ability through formal instruction and learning.

This study did zero-in on the perception of college students in St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Dipolog City towards entrepreneurship education (EE), entrepreneurial competence (EC), and entrepreneurial intentions (EI).

Entrepreneurship Education

Certainly, entrepreneurship education (EE) in higher education aims to empower students with a solid knowledge base and to encourage their innovative thinking. The development of the students' general cognitions must take precedence over the enhancement of their character traits. The specialists who are prepared for professional action are created through this process (Akhmetshin, et al., 2019). Its purpose is to build profound entrepreneurial capabilities in students and to prepare them for entrepreneurial practice (Tittel & Terzidis, 2020).

Additionally, entrepreneurship education accomplishes an important educational goal by fostering students' development as educated on entrepreneurship before shifting

their attention to organizational professions, which look like a safer and less demanding option. Despite being frequently linked to neo-liberal ideologies, it can nonetheless support students in making autonomous decisions regarding their professions (Walmsley, et al., 2018). Moreover, Fayolle (2018) explained that the study of entrepreneurship is expanding globally, and entrepreneurship courses need to be strengthened through solid intellectual and conceptual underpinnings and critically examine researchers' and teachers' activities.

Obviously, entrepreneurship is frequently taught as if it were a natural science, according to Neck and Greene (2011) as cited by Linton & Klinton (2019). They claim that there are many similarities between business owners and designers, and that business owners "think and act somewhat like designers." Universities and colleges provide entrepreneurship education courses to help people develop their entrepreneurial abilities and get ready to engage in business activities. However, the rising body of research on the influence of EE yields diverse and seemingly at odds findings. The current study adds to this body of work by identifying the approach of EE. Furthermore, the features of students' exposure to an entrepreneurial family may be considered as factor that helps explain the results of EE (Hahn et al., 2020).

As to the instruction, one broader view reveals that entrepreneurship instruction employs a variety of teaching techniques, from cooperative learning using project work and theater pedagogy to practice businesses and company visits (Ruskovaara & Pihkala, 2015). These activities would more entice students to venture into business undertaking in the future. Also, students are more likely to launch a business when taking classes that prioritize acquiring skills and competency (Nabi et al. 2017, cited by Linton & Klinton, 2019).

Entrepreneurial Competence

One possible effect of entrepreneurship education is the enhanced level of entrepreneurial competence of students and graduates of business programs where entrepreneurship subjects are part of their curriculum. Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) as cited by Esubalew & Raghurama (2020) defined entrepreneurial competence as a person's capacity to find, develop, and use resources for specific commercial purposes. Very clearly that it is an amalgam of knowledge, skills, abilities, beliefs, attitudes, personality and expertise of the individual that leads to entrepreneurial activity. In addition, for a person to carry out a specific work, appropriate motivations and required personal attributes are essential. Entrepreneurial skills therefore determine an entrepreneur's success. He can be anticipated to succeed in his entrepreneurial endeavors if he possesses all of these skills. A business venture's capacity to succeed depends on the project's intrinsic viability as well as to how it is organized, carried out, and managed. The majority of the tasks involved in designing, implementing, and managing a business are handled by the business owner or manager. The motivation for carrying out these chores comes from him or her.

Notably, the entrepreneur needs to possess specific knowledge, abilities, and a suitable personality type in order to carry out effectively the business opportunity they have in mind. These might all be referred to as competencies when taken all together which can be acquired through entrepreneurship education in colleges and universities. Mahendra, Djatmatika, and Hermawan (2017) as cited by Adeyamo et al. (2021) affirms that entrepreneurial competence is positively linked to entrepreneurship education. The impact of entrepreneurship education on students' entrepreneurial aptitude is substantial (Adeyamo et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurial Intentions

Another possible outcome of entrepreneurship education is the entrepreneurial intentions (EI) of students. Entrepreneurial intentions are brought about by entrepreneurial education which pertains to whole education and training activity whether it is an educational system or non-educational system (Liñán, 2004 cited by Li & Wu, 2019). Entrepreneurship education's role to forge and enhance entrepreneurial intentions is vital. Yi (2020) defined EI as a person's perception of the effects of their actions as well as their likelihood of believing in themselves, being effective, and taking advantage of business opportunities. This considers aspiration, unshakable dedication, and a desire for independence. Definitely, EI is the deliberate mental state that comes before doing something and focuses on entrepreneurial activities like starting a new business and becoming an entrepreneur. This goes to show also that entrepreneurship serves as a career option or as a career pathway by some students and graduates. The study of Iwu et al. (2020) explained that students have the desire to become entrepreneurs after finishing their tertiary education.

Clearly, entrepreneurship is as well considered as a career option for some people specially college graduates. An entrepreneurial job gives a wide range of experience, sharpens analytical and communication abilities, gives a platform to deal with a variety of business issues, industries, and businesses, and gives the chance to discover what the world requires and how can a solution be created.

While most studies focused on entrepreneurial programs in colleges and universities, the researchers deemed that there is a need to explore how entrepreneurship education impacts students in diverse educational programs.

St. Vincent's College Incorporated adhered to the memorandum order of the Commission on Higher Education of the Philippines that entrepreneurship courses be integrated in Bachelor of Science in Business Administration with specialization in Financial Management, Human Resource Management, and Marketing Management; Bachelor of Science in Office Administration; Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management; and Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management.

The current curriculum of the aforementioned academic programs included entrepreneurship courses specifically entrepreneurship in Tourism and Hospitality, Entrepreneurial Behavior, and Entrepreneurial Management guided by the issuances of

the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) of the Republic of the Philippines. Clearly, in the provision of CHED's Memorandum Order (CMO), it strongly suggested that the abovementioned courses be included in Higher Education Institutions' (HEI) business academic programs. The order pertains to the Policies, Standards and Guidelines labeled as CMO 17, CMO 19, CMO 62, all were in series of 2017 for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA), Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSMT), and Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), respectively.

In view of the aforementioned information, the researcher assessed the levels of entrepreneurship education (EE), entrepreneurial competence (EC), and entrepreneurial intentions (EI) of the college students with different field of specialization. The result of the evaluation served as basis for the proposed enhanced curriculum particularly in the aspects of teaching strategies and methodology.

Research Questions

The main problem of the study was to assess the students' levels of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial competence, and entrepreneurial intentions among college students of St. Vincent's College Incorporated. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 year level; and
 - 1.4 academic program?
2. What are the students' levels of entrepreneurial education (EE) when grouped according to profile?
3. Are there significant differences in the students' level of entrepreneurship education (EE) when grouped according to profile?
4. What are the students' levels of entrepreneurial competence (EC)?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' level of entrepreneurship education and their level of entrepreneurial competence?
6. What are the students' levels of entrepreneurial intentions (EI)?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the students' level of entrepreneurship education and their level of entrepreneurial intentions?
8. What entrepreneurship curriculum enhancement may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study conducted was confined in the vicinity of St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Main Campus in Dipolog City. The study did not use sampling procedure because the size of the population was not large. Instead, a census was conducted that involved a total of 105 students who finished entrepreneurship subjects or courses in the first and second semesters respectively of the school year 2022-2023. However, only a

hundred (100) students who were able to participate in the said census. The five (5) others were not able to participate due to their unavailability.

The researcher used descriptive-correlational methods with a survey as the primary tool for collecting data. The choice of a descriptive-correlational research design in the study titled “Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Competence, and Entrepreneurial Intentions Among College Students: Basis for Curriculum Enhancement” is driven by need to explore the levels and relationships among the key variables in the entrepreneurial domain. This design examined how entrepreneurship education influence entrepreneurial competence and intentions, providing information on potential associations without intervening in the natural development of these phenomena. In addition, this research design enabled quantification of the strength and direction of correlations that affords significant insights into the movements that may affect students’ competence and intentions in entrepreneurship.

The descriptive and correlational approaches considered different factors that contributed to entrepreneurial outcomes. Finally, this research design is appropriate because it provided practical insights into the interaction between entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial intentions of college students, offering essential implications for improving the curriculum of business programs particularly on the enhancement of syllabus and teaching approaches for entrepreneurship.

In order to achieve thoroughness and accuracy in this study, a careful data collection process was conducted to gather information pertinent to our research objectives. Utilizing structured surveys, the researchers collected quantitative data from the entire population to ensure comprehensive analysis of the variables which were the focus of the study. The survey instrument was conscientiously designed and validated to ascertain its appropriateness in order to measure the intended constructs accurately. Strict compliance to standardized procedures, including precise instruction and consistent administration was observed to avoid biases and ensure reliability of the collected data. The consequent dataset served as the essential elements for rigorous statistical analyses, reinforcing the internal validity of the study that contributed meaningful information into the phenomena under investigation. Through this systematic method, the study intended to give significant and empirically ground results to the scientific discussion in our field.

The research instrument assessed the independent variable which was the entrepreneurship education, and the dependent variables which were the entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial intentions. It was a modified research instrument which consisted of questions adapted from the works of different researchers who had published their research output in the online research publication journal. The questionnaire was divided into four (4) parts. Part one of which pertains to the profile of the respondents consisted of four (4) items, part two contained twenty (20) items for entrepreneurship education, part three included twenty-two (22) items for entrepreneurial competence, and part four comprised of twenty (20) items. The questionnaire was pre-tested to thirty (30)

non-respondents to get the reliability and was presented to three experts in the field to determine its content validity. The reliability and validity of the instruments were found high. The questionnaire utilized a four (4) point Likert Scale where, four (4) as the highest level of agreement, and described as Strongly Agree, followed by three (3) for Agree, two (2) for Disagree, and one (1) for Strongly Disagree, and described as the lowest level of agreement.

The Entrepreneurship Education Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the students' level of entrepreneurship education. The questionnaire contains twenty items. The following qualitative equivalents were used to interpret the students' level of entrepreneurship education.

High Level of Entrepreneurship Education (3.25 - 4.00). Students exhibited great understanding of entrepreneurship concepts, principles, and practices. They had likely received inclusive training and education about entrepreneurship that includes courses, workshops, and hands-on. They had comprehensive knowledge of business planning, market analysis, financial management, and other important aspects of entrepreneurship. They were well-prepared to pursue business opportunities and demonstrate their knowledge effectively.

Moderate Level Entrepreneurship Education (2.50 - 3.24). Students demonstrated a better grasp of entrepreneurship concepts and principles, but their knowledge may not be as comprehensive as those in the very high level. They had likely received some form of entrepreneurship education, either through coursework or practical experiences. They were familiar with the fundamental elements of entrepreneurship and had the foundation to engage entrepreneurial endeavors. They can develop further their entrepreneurial skills and knowledge with continuous learning.

Basic Level of Entrepreneurship Education (1.75 - 2.49). Students may have learned entrepreneurship concepts and principles, but their grasp may be limited. They may have engaged in a few introductory courses or workshops. Nevertheless, more education and training will increase their understanding of entrepreneurship and its application.

Low Level of Entrepreneurship Education (1.00 – 1.74). Students had very little exposure to entrepreneurship concepts and principles. They may not have engaged in any formal entrepreneurship courses or exposed to relevant educational activities. Essential interventions and opportunities would help these students to develop further the basics of entrepreneurship.

The Entrepreneurial Competence Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the students' level of entrepreneurial competence. The questionnaire contains twenty items. The following qualitative equivalents were used to interpret the students' level of entrepreneurial competence.

High Level of Entrepreneurial Competence (3.25 – 4.00): Students exhibited superior skills and abilities relative to entrepreneurship. They had a solid understanding of business management, strategic planning, decision-making, and problem-solving. They demonstrate excellent leadership qualities, effective communication skills, and flexibility under changing business environments. They had the capability to use practical knowledge and skills to face entrepreneurial challenges and drive business growth.

Moderate Level Entrepreneurial Competence (2.50 – 3.24). Students demonstrated solid skills and abilities in different aspects of entrepreneurship. They had a good understanding of business management fundamentals and show competence in critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork. They were capable of putting into practice their knowledge to start and manage entrepreneurial activities, although they may improve them through constant learning and experience.

Basic Level of Entrepreneurial Competence (1.75 – 2.49). Students demonstrated a relatively basic level of entrepreneurial competence. They may possess some fundamental skills and abilities about entrepreneurship, but such were limited. More training and practical experiences were required to enhance their skills in aspects of business planning, leadership, marketing, and financial management.

Low Level of Entrepreneurial Competence (1.00 – 1.74): Students exhibited minimal skills and abilities related to entrepreneurship. They may lack the basic knowledge and practical experience in business management, decision-making, and problem-solving. Their entrepreneurial competence may be enhanced through essential training and support.

The Entrepreneurial Intentions Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the students' level of entrepreneurial competence. The questionnaire contains twenty items. The following qualitative equivalents were used to interpret the students' level of entrepreneurial intentions.

High Level of Entrepreneurial Intention (3.25 – 4.00): Students had a robust desire and commitment to start and develop their own business ventures. They actively look for entrepreneurial opportunities, and had clear goals, and showed a high level of motivation to follow entrepreneurship as a career path. They had a well-defined vision and were determined to take steps that will turn their ideas into successful businesses activities.

Moderate Level of Entrepreneurial Intention (2.50 – 3.24): Students exhibited remarkable interest in entrepreneurship, and showed a desire to start their own business ventures. They may have some specific business concepts or aspirations, and were open to pursue entrepreneurial opportunities. They displayed a certain level of motivation and were willing to consider entrepreneurship as a viable career choice.

Basic Level of Entrepreneurial Intention (1.75 – 2.49): Students demonstrated a relatively basic level of entrepreneurial intentions. While they may have some interest in entrepreneurship, their commitment and determination to pursue it as a career may be

limited. They may have a more uncertain stance towards starting their own business venture or may choose other career options. Additional guidance and support may help them to further develop their entrepreneurial intentions.

Low Level of Entrepreneurial Intention (1.00 – 1.74): Students exhibited a low level of entrepreneurial intentions. They had small interest or desire to embark on entrepreneurship as a career choice. They may have a preference for conventional employment or have other career desires other than for entrepreneurship. Encouragement and exposure to entrepreneurial opportunities may help to activate their interest and intentions in entrepreneurship.

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data collected for this study:

Percentage was used to determine the demographic profile of students. Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the students' level entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial competence and intentions.

Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis H Test were used to determine if the differences in the students' level of entrepreneurship education were significant or not.

Spearman-Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationship between the students' entrepreneurship education and their entrepreneurial competence and intentions.

The data were analyzed using MS Excel and Jamovi v. 2.3.19. The relationship was tested using a .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The students' profile in terms of age, sex, year level, and academic program is shown in Table 1. The table shows the profile, frequency, and percent.

Table 1

Students' Profile

PROFILE	Frequency	Percent
Age		
21 – 22 years old	29	29.0
22 – 23 years old	53	53.0
24 – 25 years old	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0
Sex		
Female	68	68.0
Male	32	32.0
	931	

Total	100	100.0
Year Level		
Second Year	5	5.0
Third Year	33	33.0
Fourth Year	62	62.0
Total	100	100.0
Academic Program		
BSBA – FM	38	38.0
BSBA – HRM	5	5.0
BSBA – MM	25	25.0
BSHM	5	5.0
BSOA	5	5.0
BSTM	22	22.0
Total	100	100.0

The students' levels of entrepreneurship education is shown in Table 2. The table shows the statements, mean, standard deviation (SD), and interpretation.

Table 2

Students' Levels of Entrepreneurship Education

	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
EE1	Entrepreneurship education has provided me a new and different experience.	3.66	0.48	High Level
EE2	The entrepreneurship education has provided me an opportunity to learn by doing.	3.54	0.50	High Level
EE3	As a result of the study of entrepreneurship education, I have better understanding of business ventures.	3.53	0.54	High Level
EE4	The entrepreneurship education has developed entrepreneurial knowledge and skills in students.	3.62	0.53	High Level
EE5	The entrepreneurship education has raised interest towards Entrepreneurship.	3.43	0.52	High Level
EE6	I enjoyed lectures on entrepreneurship.	3.51	0.60	High Level
EE7	Lectures on entrepreneurship I received have increased my interest to pursue an entrepreneurial career.	3.43	0.56	High Level
EE8	The entrepreneurship education course I have undergone has prepared me to make informed decisions on entrepreneurial career choices.	3.51	0.52	High Level
EE9	I am happy to have experienced entrepreneurship education.	3.70	0.50	High Level

EE10	The entrepreneurship education that I received has encouraged me to venture into entrepreneurship after graduation.	3.42	0.54	High Level
EE11	My entrepreneurship lecturers helped me meet and interact with successful entrepreneurs.	3.36	0.60	High Level
EE12	The entrepreneurship course enabled me to identify business related opportunities.	3.48	0.50	High Level
EE13	The entrepreneurship course has taught me how to create services and/or products that can satisfy the needs of customers.	3.49	0.52	High Level
EE14	Entrepreneurship course has taught me on how develop business plans successfully.	3.42	0.52	High Level
EE15	Due to the entrepreneurship education course, I now have skills to create a new business.	3.29	0.56	High Level
EE16	With the entrepreneurship education course I had undergone, I can now successfully identify sources of business finance.	3.26	0.56	High Level
EE17	Entrepreneurship education course has taught me how to perform feasibility studies.	3.29	0.50	High Level
EE18	Entrepreneurship course has stimulated my interest in entrepreneurship.	3.37	0.58	High Level
EE19	Entrepreneurship course has improved my skills, knowledge and interest about entrepreneurship.	3.55	0.54	High Level
EE20	Overall, I am very satisfied with how entrepreneurship education course is being taught.	3.58	0.54	High Level
Overall		3.47	0.53	High Level

Table 3 presents the difference in the students' levels of entrepreneurship education (EE) when grouped according to profile. The table shows the profile, U-value, H-value, P-value, and interpretation.

Table 3

Test of Difference in the Students' Levels of Entrepreneurship Education by Profile

Profile	U-Value	H-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Age	–	3.81	.149	Not Significant
Sex	1047	–	.764	Not Significant
Year Level	–	4.41	.110	Not Significant
Academic Program	–	5.90	.316	Not Significant

The students' level of entrepreneurial competence is shown in Table 4. The table shows the statements, mean, standard deviation (SD), and interpretation.

Table 4

Students' Level of Entrepreneurial Competence

	Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
EC1	As a result of entrepreneurship education, I can develop ideas to improve existing products.	3.35	0.54	High Level
EC2	I am skilled at establishing contacts and networks.	3.08	0.61	Moderate Level
EC3	I like to work in a group and I am able to lead it.	3.13	0.64	Moderate Level
EC4	As a result of entrepreneurship education, I was able to find solutions to existing problems in business.	3.27	0.58	High Level
EC5	I define goals and priorities to meet my objectives.	3.33	0.53	High Level
EC6	I foresee the needed resources to perform my tasks about starting a business.	3.30	0.57	High Level
EC7	When I plan, I take unforeseen events into account.	3.17	0.57	Moderate Level
EC8	I set dates to complete tasks and keep them.	3.31	0.64	High Level
EC9	I carry out my work as well as possible, always maintaining the same level of quality in what I do.	3.40	0.58	High Level
EC10	I reach agreements and obtain commitments from others.	3.31	0.60	High Level
EC11	I visualize and easily manage key points in negotiations with my colleagues.	3.24	0.57	Moderate Level
EC12	I am reasonably good with words and can use them to generate emotions to convince and influence others.	3.15	0.61	Moderate Level
EC13	I can bring different ideas to action plans to solve problems, innovate, and enhance processes or products.	3.24	0.59	Moderate Level
EC14	I facilitate a climate of open communication, motivating and encouraging the members of my team.	3.25	0.52	High Level
EC15	I am able to work independently.	3.28	0.62	High Level

EC16	I express my point of view and stand by my position.	3.31	0.60	High Level
EC17	I developed and execute action plans until I reach the expected outcome.	3.32	0.53	High Level
EC18	I persist with my action plan even in the face of adversity.	3.22	0.56	Moderate Level
EC19	I stand by my ideas and am not easily persuaded otherwise.	3.19	0.60	Moderate Level
EC20	I take control of my work efficiently.	3.34	0.55	High Level
EC21	I take responsibility for the outcomes of my actions.	3.49	0.54	High Level
EC22	I seek opportunities and adopt initiatives to turn these opportunities into results.	3.47	0.57	High Level
Overall		3.28	0.58	High Level

Table 5 presents the test of relationship between the *students' levels of entrepreneurship education and their levels of entrepreneurial competence*. The table shows the variables, computed ρ , P-value, and interpretation.

Table 5

Test of Relationship between the Students' Levels of Entrepreneurship Education and Their Levels of Entrepreneurial Competence

Variables	Computed ρ	P-Value	Interpretation
<i>Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Competence</i>	.690	<.001	High Correlation/ Significant

The students' level of entrepreneurial intentions is shown in Table 6. The table shows the statements, mean, standard deviation (SD), and interpretation.

Table 6*Students' Level of Entrepreneurial Intentions*

	Statements	Mean	SD	Implication
EI1	Starting a firm and keeping it viable would be easy for me.	2.97	0.61	Moderate Level
EI2	A career as an entrepreneur is totally attractive to me.	3.37	0.54	High Level
EI3	My friends would approve of my decision to start a business.	3.35	0.61	High Level
EI4	I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur.	3.29	0.62	High Level
EI5	I believe I would be able to start a business.	3.40	0.55	High Level
EI6	I will make every effort to start and run my own business.	3.47	0.61	High Level
EI7	I am able to control the creation process of a new business.	3.24	0.55	Moderate Level
EI8	My immediate family would approve my decision to start a business.	3.37	0.66	High Level
EI9	I have no doubts of ever starting my own business.	3.18	0.68	Moderate Level
EI10	If I had the opportunity and resources, I would love to start a business.	3.44	0.61	High Level
EI11	My colleagues would approve of my decision to start a business.	3.35	0.59	High Level
EI12	Amongst various options, I would rather be anything but an entrepreneur.	3.23	0.63	Moderate Level
EI13	I am determined to create a business venture in the future.	3.52	0.56	High Level
EI14	If I tried to start a business, I would have a high chance of being successful.	3.26	0.66	High Level
EI15	Being an entrepreneur would give me great satisfaction	3.35	0.59	High Level
EI16	It would be very easy for me to develop a business idea.	3.20	0.68	Moderate Level
EI17	My professional goals is to be an entrepreneur.	3.31	0.63	High Level
EI18	Being an entrepreneur implies more advantages than disadvantages to me.	3.31	0.61	High Level

E119	I have a very high intention of ever starting a business.	3.37	0.56	High Level
E120	I know all about the practical details needed to start a business.	3.15	0.64	Moderate Level
Overall		3.31	0.61	High Level

Table 7 presents the test of relationship between the *students' levels of entrepreneurship education and their levels of entrepreneurial intentions*. The table shows the variables, computed ρ , P-value, and interpretation.

Table 7

Test of Relationship between the Students' Levels of Entrepreneurship Education and Their Levels of Entrepreneurial Competence

Variables	Computed ρ	P-Value	Interpretation
<i>Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions</i>	.657	<.001	High Correlation/ Significant

DISCUSSION

In Table 1, The students' profile by age showed that majority of the participants were in the age group twenty-two (22) to twenty-three (23) years old. This means that the bulk of the participation was in this age group. It was also observed that age group twenty (20) to twenty-one (21) had few participants, and quite very few participants were in the age range of twenty (24) to twenty-five (25) years old. This was an expected scenario considering the that the entrepreneurship courses were offered at higher year level. The results also showed that majority of the participants were female students. This means that female students got higher level of participation in this study. It can be noted that entrepreneurship courses were dominated by females. On the contrary, in the study of Petridou, Sarri, and Kyrgidou (2009), there were more male students than female ones. Nonetheless, females were substantially more interested than men in learning new things, growing their abilities, competing in the workplace, and making connections with nearby businesses when it comes to their attitudes on taking part in entrepreneurial educational programs. A significant result of this study was the participation of second-year students, constituting 5% of the total participants. This was expected considering that the entrepreneurship courses were offered in the third year and fourth year levels. Though few, these early-stage participants add a dynamic element to the research, importantly showcasing the effect of early exposure to entrepreneurship education on the developing minds of these students. Investigating the responses and perceptions of second-year participants could uncover valuable insights into the initial stages of their entrepreneurial journey. Nevertheless, the thirty-three percent (33%) and sixty-two percent (62%) were

third year and fourth year student participants, respectively. This suggested that at this year levels, many students were exposed to entrepreneurial training and learning in the hope of strengthening their entrepreneurial ability and desire. These entrepreneurial ability and desire were believed to be essential for someone to succeed in any business venture he or she might engage in after finishing college education. Moreover, the results showed that the profile of the respondents in terms of the academic program, based on the tabulated data, thirty-eight (38) or 38% of the participants were BSBA specializing in Financial Management, five (5) or 5% were BSBA specializing in Human Resource Management, twenty-five (25) or 25% were BSBA specializing in Marketing Management, five (5) or 5% were BSHM, five (5) or 5% were BSOA, and twenty-two (22) or 22% were BSTM students. This means that entrepreneurship courses were mostly attended by BSBA major in financial management, BSBA major in marketing management and BSTM students. Other academic programs such as BSBA major in human resource management, BSOA, and BSHM had few numbers.

It can be observed in Table 2 that each of the statements had variations in their mean scores. Despite the variations, students' level of entrepreneurship education (EE) per item was high, and statements were rated strongly agree. Overall, students' level of entrepreneurship education was high. The high level of students' EE indicated participants's great grasp of entrepreneurship concepts, principles, and practices through training and education. They had general knowledge of how to do business planning, analysis of the market and managing the finances of the business venture. They think entrepreneurship education was essential for anyone wanting to be a successful entrepreneur.

In Table 3, significant difference in the students' levels of entrepreneurship education according to profile were tested. The Kruskal Wallis H Test results, $H(2) = 3.81$, $p = .149$ in the table shows a p-value greater than .05 level of significance. This means that there was no significant difference in the students' levels of entrepreneurship education by age. This implies that the students' levels of entrepreneurship education were similar regardless of age group. The students showed a great grasp of the entrepreneurship concepts, principles and practices due to the training and education they experienced. Students from the three (3) age groups had good understanding of business planning, market analysis and managing the finances of the enterprise.

The table also shows the Mann-Whitney U test results, $U = 1047$, $p = .764$ and had a p-value greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was enough evidence to deduce insignificant differences of male and female students' levels of entrepreneurship education (EE). The students' levels of entrepreneurship education (EE) revealed variations in their respective mean scores. However, the said variation was insignificant at all as manifested in the result of test of difference. This connotes immaterial difference in EE of both sexes. The EE levels were rated strongly agree by these groups. This further indicated that both male and females exhibited significant understanding about entrepreneurship, its principles and practices. Both sexes had obtained comprehensive knowledge about business planning, market and financial analysis which were very important to ensure a successful business in the future.

Also in Table 3, Kruskal-Wallis H Test results, $H(2) = 4.41$, $p = .110$ showed a p-value greater than .05 level of significance. This means that there was no significant difference in the levels of entrepreneurship education when they were grouped according to their year levels. This means further that across year level, students had likely received general knowledge about entrepreneurship including its principles, concepts and practices. Included in this knowledge as well is about conducting a market analysis, and about financial and marketing management which vital to make the business endeavor a success.

Kruskal-Wallis H Test results $H(2) = 5.90$, $p = .316$ in Table 3 show a p-value greater than 0.05 level of significance. There was no significant difference in the students' EE levels in terms of their academic programs. This implied that EE levels of students when grouped according to academic programs had no material difference. Though data analyses showed variations of the mean scores of students' EE level by academic programs, they were not significant at all. This implied further that BSBA-FM, BSBA-HRM, BSBA-MM, BSOA, BSHM, and BSTM students had high levels of EE. They had likely undergone education and training that equipped them entrepreneurial concepts, principles and practices which included knowledge about market analysis, business planning, marketing and financial management which were very essential to make the business endeavor work. With entrepreneurship education, they were well prepared to explore business opportunities.

Table 4 were the results of students' level of entrepreneurial competence (EC) per statement. As shown in the table, each of the statements had differences in their respective mean scores as well as in their EC levels. Moreover, a couple of statements had moderate EC levels and were rated agree, and several statements also had high EC levels and were rated strongly agree. Despite the observed differences, the overall EC level was high. This implied that students possess superior ability pertaining to entrepreneurship wherein they had strong understanding of managing business, strategic planning process, decision-making and solving problems in business. They exhibited great leadership ability, effective skills in communication, and adaptability to dynamic business environments. They had the capacity to utilize practical knowledge and solve entrepreneurial problems geared towards business development.

The results of Spearman's Rho Correlation in Table 5, $\rho = .690$, $p < .001$, showed that there was a high correlation between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial competence, and a p-value lower than .05. This means that there was a significant relationship between the students' levels of entrepreneurship education and their levels of entrepreneurial competence. The findings further suggested that when the entrepreneurship education level increases, the level of students' entrepreneurial competence will also increase. The finding of this study pertaining to the association between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial competence agreed with the findings of several authors. Roxas (2014) said finishing an entrepreneurship course has an impact on business students' knowledge about entrepreneurship, their view towards starting a business, and their belief that they can perform specific entrepreneurial tasks and attain goals. While Wang, Yueh, & Wen (2019) on their research reported a positive

impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial competence particularly in the aspect of skills. The research of Tittel & Terzidis (2020) found as well that entrepreneurship education develops entrepreneurial competence that eventually increases entrepreneurial desire.

One of the very reasons this study was conducted was to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial competence anchored on human capital theory. The results of this inquiry manifested a significant and positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial competence that supported the concept of human capital theory applied to entrepreneurship. Human capital theory postulated that productivity and economic results of individuals can be enhanced through gaining knowledge, skills, and abilities by way of education and training. It implied the essential task of entrepreneurship education with respect to developing the vital competencies of individuals for a fruitful entrepreneurial endeavor. The outcomes of this inquiry were consonant to the tenets of human capital theory asserting entrepreneurial competence was essentially influenced by entrepreneurship education. It indicated that the ability of the individuals in seizing and taking advantage of business opportunities, managing business risk, and growing the business venture were enhanced through appropriate knowledge, skills and attitudes being acquired. This discovery highlights the essence of developing human capital through entrepreneurship education to achieve competence in the field of entrepreneurship. The strong and significant relationship discovered between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial competence provides empirical backup for the worth to invest in entrepreneurship education as tool to nurture human capital. The findings underscore the significance of integrating an improved entrepreneurship-related courses into the curricula.

Shown in Table 6 were the results of the tabulated data pertaining to students' levels of entrepreneurial intentions (EI) for every statement. Each of the statements had different mean scores. It was noticed that there were items having moderate levels of EI and were rated agree, while majority of the items resulted to high level of EI and were rated strongly agree. Overall, the students' EI level was high. A high EI indicates that students possessed a strong commitment and desire to engage in business venture and would look for business opportunities. They had clear goals and high level of motivation to pursue a career in entrepreneurship. They had well-established vision and eager to convert their ideas into successful business. The students were extremely committed to starting his own business and plans to do so soon.

Spearman's Rho Correlation results, $\rho = .657$, $p < .001$, in Table 7 revealed a high correlation between those key variables. Results also showed that p-value was less than .05 level of significance. This means that there was a significant relationship between the students' levels of entrepreneurship education and their levels of entrepreneurial intentions. Results indicated that as the level of entrepreneurship education increases, the level of entrepreneurial intention also increases among students.

This converges the results of the study of other researchers. The studies of Doan and Phan (2020), and Jeana (2020) pointed out a strong influence of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention. Students' intention to start their own business is influenced positively by entrepreneurship education (Ahmed et al., 2020). While Walter & Block (2016) in their research found very strong relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention. However, the effect of EE on EI fluctuates (Nabi et al., 2016).

Notably, the study was intended to probe the association between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention of college students enrolled in entrepreneurship courses using the model of Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). The TPB suggested that individuals' intention to engage in a particular behavior like entrepreneurship, were influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavior control. By evaluating entrepreneurship education in molding these factors, it was the objective of this study to have a deeper understanding of how educational interventions could potentially contribute to the development of entrepreneurial intentions.

The findings of this study confirmed the proposition that entrepreneurship education had a positive influence on individuals' attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Through involvement in entrepreneurship-related coursework, and opportunities for experiential learnings, students gain knowledge, skills, and solid understanding of entrepreneurship as a feasible career option. This knowledge and better attitude about entrepreneurship can contribute to the development of entrepreneurial intentions.

Additionally, the outcome of this study showed the importance of subjective norms in the association between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention. Students who experience entrepreneurship education were likely to be exposed to a social environment that promoted and encouraged entrepreneurial undertakings. The interaction among peers, networking activities, mentoring programs, and business planning process facilitated through entrepreneurship education afford social norms that foster an encouraging entrepreneurial culture.

Another important point that this study considered, was the role of perceived behavioral control on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention. Entrepreneurship education provided individuals the knowledge, skills, ideas, and resources to begin and successfully manage a business. This improved perceived control on the entrepreneurial process fortifies individual's confidence in the capacity to deal with entrepreneurial activities. Consequently, individuals who had gone through entrepreneurship education were more likely to have solid entrepreneurial intentions.

The results of this investigation had impact for school administrators, practitioners and educators directly or indirectly involved in entrepreneurship education programs. Through in-depth understanding of the essential role of entrepreneurship education in forming attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, stakeholders can design and implement educational programs that will develop entrepreneurial intentions.

Practical experiences, networking opportunities, and utilizing successful entrepreneurs or guest speakers should be integrated into the entrepreneurship curriculum.

By and large, this study added to the body of knowledge about the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention grounded on the Theory of Planned Behavior. The results underscore the significance of entrepreneurship education in forming the attitudes of individuals, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which in turn influence their entrepreneurial intentions. Utilizing the findings of this study, stakeholders can develop entrepreneurship education activities and foster an entrepreneurial culture. Future studies should continue to discover the dynamic nature of this relationships and the sustainable results of entrepreneurship education on actual entrepreneurial behavior.

Proposed Enhancement of the Curriculum for Entrepreneurship Courses

A curriculum for business program is a structured and extensive set of courses designed to share knowledge and skills in different areas of business, making students ready for careers in the dynamic and vast field of trade and commerce. In view of the results of this study, it is imperative to enhance the curriculum concentrating on the improvement of the syllabus for entrepreneurship courses making it more contextualized. The syllabus for entrepreneurship courses smoothly integrates with the business program, giving students a combination of theoretical knowledge and practical know-how important for determining opportunities, creating innovating solutions and successfully starting and managing business venture in the very dynamic business environment. The syllabus is significant in a business program because it affords students with the knowledge and skills to promote creativity, cultivate a proactive mindset, and deal with the challenging business landscape, ultimately be motivated to innovate and contribute to sustainable economic development.

Moreover, improvement of the entrepreneurship syllabus is necessary to better align with the changing business landscape, ascertaining students are equipped not only with fundamental knowledge but also with skills and insights essential in facing the challenges and opportunities of the dynamic business environment. In a dynamic business landscape, promoting entrepreneurship is essential for individuals to be fully equipped with the mindset, knowledge and skills to respond to challenges, seize opportunities, and practice innovation. The proposed syllabus enhancement for entrepreneurship courses intends to afford and empower students with more relevant learning experience that goes beyond the conventional way. By combining theoretical frameworks with hands-on experiential learning, actual case studies and interactive mentorship, these improvements would really develop not just practical know-how required to plan, establish and sustain business ventures, but also the needed critical thinking ability, and flexibility necessary to survive in a very volatile business environment. With the improved syllabus, we can produce new generation of visionary and skilled entrepreneurs. The following may be considered and incorporated into the syllabus to increase further the level of entrepreneurship education (EE), entrepreneurial competence (EC) and entrepreneurial intention (EI):

- a. **Relevant and Updated Course Contents:** These contents should cover topics such as ideation, market research, business planning, financial management, operations management, human resource management and marketing management. By studying these topics, students will become equipped with the right mindset, knowledge and skills that are vital for starting and growing a business venture.
- b. **Encourage Creativity and Innovation:** Encouraging creativity and innovation can help students produce novel business concepts. This can be undertaken by requiring students to do brainstorming, collaboration and experimentation with different methods of solving business-related problems.
- c. **Mentorship:** Experienced and successful entrepreneurs can provide guidance and motivation which can be an effective approach to improve students' entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial intention. These experienced entrepreneurs would serve as mentors too who will provide input, and advice about practical business strategy, financing, and networking.
- d. **Provide Hands-On Experience:** Providing students with hands-on experience in entrepreneurship can help them develop the practical skills they need to succeed. This can be done by offering internships, co-op programs, and other opportunities for students to work with startups and small businesses.

With practical and project-based experience in place in the enhanced curriculum, it affords students to develop and apply their knowledge about entrepreneurship in a more engaging way. Connections with entrepreneurs in town and feedback and success stories of business people would certainly help students as their inspiration and motivation. With it, they can gain significant insights into the dynamic and challenging business landscape and opportunities of business venture.

e. Utilization of Entrepreneurship Laboratory

Objective: The Entrepreneurship Laboratory is designed to provide students with hands-on experience in entrepreneurship by giving them opportunities to develop, launch, and operate their own business ventures in a supportive, collaborative environment.

Overview: The Entrepreneurship Laboratory is a dedicated space within the school campus that provides students with access to resources, mentorship, and funding to support their entrepreneurial endeavors. The laboratory is staffed by experienced entrepreneurs, business coaches and teachers, and industry professionals who provide guidance and support to students as they develop their ideas, launch their businesses, and navigate the challenges of entrepreneurship.

Facilities and Resources: The Entrepreneurship Laboratory provides a range of facilities and resources to support student ventures, including:

Workspace: The laboratory provides workspace and meeting rooms for students to collaborate and work on their ventures.

Mentorship: The laboratory provides students with access to experienced mentors who can provide guidance and support in various areas of business development, including product development, marketing, and fundraising.

Educational Programs: The laboratory provides educational programs, including workshops, seminars, and training sessions, to help students build skills and knowledge in entrepreneurship.

Operations and Management: The Entrepreneurship Laboratory is managed by a team of students with the guidance and supervision of entrepreneurship teachers. The management team is responsible for overseeing the day-to-day operations of the laboratory, including:

- a. Providing mentorship and coaching to students.
- b. Managing the facilities and resources of the laboratory.
- c. Developing and delivering educational programs.
- d. Marketing and promoting the laboratory to attract students.
- e. Equity investments from the laboratory's management team and student investors.
- f. The laboratory aims to achieve sustainability by charging students affordable rent for their workspace and facilities.

The Entrepreneurship Laboratory provides a supportive environment for students to develop their entrepreneurial skills, launch their own businesses, and learn from experienced mentors and industry professionals. By providing access to funding, mentorship, and educational programs, the laboratory helps students overcome common challenges and achieve their goals. The laboratory is managed by a team of experienced professionals who are committed to fostering innovation, collaboration, and entrepreneurship among students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that majority of the participants were in the age group twenty-two (22) to twenty-three (23) years old. This means that the bulk of the participation was in this age group. The results also showed that majority of the participants were female students. This means that female students got higher level of participation in this study. Many students were exposed to entrepreneurial training and learning in the higher levels in the hope of strengthening their entrepreneurial ability and desire. Entrepreneurship courses were mostly attended by BSBA major in financial management, BSBA major in marketing management and BSTM students.

The students have superior ability pertaining to entrepreneurship wherein they had strong understanding of managing business, strategic planning process, decision-making and solving problems in business. They had the general knowledge of how to do business planning, analysis of the market and managing the finances of the business venture. They think entrepreneurship education was essential for anyone wanting to be a successful entrepreneur. They had clear goals and high level of motivation to pursue a career in entrepreneurship. They had well-established vision and eager to convert their ideas into successful business.

Moreover, there is a measurable and meaningful connection between the education students receive in entrepreneurship and their ability to demonstrate entrepreneurial skills and knowledge and their likelihood or desire to pursue entrepreneurial activities in the future.

Recommendations

In light of the outcomes of this study, strengthening students' entrepreneurship education (EE) is essential to increase their levels of entrepreneurial competence (EC) and entrepreneurial intentions (EI). Students' enhanced EC and EI through EE can help students or graduate of a business program plan and implement business related activities. It is believed that entrepreneurship is one of the approaches that can curb unemployment issue of any country, thereby bolstering the national economy. The following recommendations are to be given due consideration.

1. Business educators considers entrepreneurship curriculum as the core guide for teaching and learning so that students have access to rigorous academic activities relative to entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship Curriculum as to its structure, organization and consideration is designed to improve the learning of students and to facilitate quality instruction. In this case, the design of the curriculum is paramount because it establishes the framework for what students will know and be able to do when they finish the academic program. In order to ensure that appropriate design of curriculum is in place, it is recommended that Higher Education Institution may conduct a regular curriculum quality audit (CQA).

CQA is a systematic evaluation of a curriculum particularly on syllabi to ascertain its alignment with program outcomes or standards. It is the process of doing rigorous evaluation of the curriculum and syllabi. This assesses how the implementation of the curriculum is done on the performance of learning and the employment of supporting means of learning activities relative to entrepreneurship. The CQA determines gaps, under and overrepresentation of the curriculum anchored on the program outcomes as the standards under the BSBA, BSOA, BSHM, and BSTM, and ascertain convergence of course learning outcomes, activities and assessment with the aforementioned standards.

2. HEI may design its syllabus for entrepreneurship courses in a more contextualized manner so as to achieve the desired program outcomes. In this respect, the following are further recommended to be considered, and incorporated in the syllabus:
 - a. Contents of the entrepreneurship courses must be constantly updated and should cover relevant topics for entrepreneurship taking into consideration the evolving business landscape and the dynamic needs of aspiring entrepreneurs.
 - b. Business simulation must be employed as a core teaching approach apart from lecture to afford practical entrepreneurial experience to students that utilizes entrepreneurship laboratory. In this set-up, lecture should only account for fifty percent (50%) of the course content, while the other fifty percent (50%) is allocated for hands-on experience. The integration of this activity into the course content bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and application in the realm of entrepreneurship.
 - c. In addition, HEI should encourage both teachers and students to organize activities that will develop the entrepreneurial mindset of students such as tour to small and medium enterprises, trade fair and exhibits. The study suggests that entrepreneurship education be improved with the goal of enhancing students' capacity for entrepreneurship and a prosperous business career.
3. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering business programs may provide for an Entrepreneurship Laboratory. The laboratory is a resource that supports students' exposure to the real world in the field of entrepreneurship. This is a specialized space and program established to promote and support innovation, and realization of business ideas. Moreover, this workspace and resources should be provided with office facilities, meeting rooms, and an area intended for product manufacturing activities. Its utilization conforms to the broader teaching methodology of experiential learning that underscores hands-on or real-world application of entrepreneurial concepts and principles. This way, students may be provided with practical engagements and opportunities to apply their entrepreneurial knowledge and demonstrate their skills in the real-world scenarios.
4. HEIs may implement the proposed informed teaching strategies for entrepreneurship courses outlined in this study aimed at increasing the levels of entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial intentions.

Further recommendations. Topics that future researchers may consider for future study are recommended. They are the following:

1. Conduct longitudinal research to track changes in entrepreneurial intentions and competencies over time. This can help identify the long-term impact of entrepreneurship education on students' career choices and entrepreneurial activities.

2. Investigate specific curriculum components that effectively enhance entrepreneurial competencies. This could include experiential learning opportunities, mentorship programs, and collaboration with local businesses.
3. Investigate how gender, socioeconomic background, and cultural diversity influence entrepreneurial intentions and competencies. This can help tailor educational programs to be more inclusive and effective.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research followed ethical principles that ensures rights, dignity and well-being of the participants are respected. Before the commencement of data collection, the researcher sought the approval of the school president of St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Dipolog City. In addition, during the course of data gathering, informed consent was secured from all participants to ascertain their full awareness of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risk, and benefits. Participants were told that their participation was voluntary, and they can withdraw without facing any adverse repercussion. In order to uphold confidentiality and privacy, all information collected during the conduct of the study was anonymized, numbers were used in lieu of their names particularly in the tabulation procedure. Further, the information was kept safe and only the researcher had access to it. The researcher took steps to guarantee that the interpretation of the findings was free from bias, and the results were utilized solely for research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Acs, Z., Åstebro, T., Audretsch, D., & Robinson, D. T. (2016). Public policy to promote entrepreneurship: a call to arms. *Small Business Economics*, 47(1), 35–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-016-9712-2>
- Adeyemo, S. A., Ogunleye, P. O., Adeyemi, M. A., & Kareem, T. S. (2021). Entrepreneurship Education as an Impetus to Entrepreneurial Competence and Entrepreneurial Intentions among Polytechnic Students: A Quantitative Approach. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2021/v17i430428>
- Ahmed, T., Chandran, V. G. R., Klobas, J. E., Liñán, F., & Kokkalis, P. (2020).

- Entrepreneurship education programmes: How learning, inspiration and resources affect intentions for new venture creation in a developing economy. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 18(1), 100327.
- Akhmetshin, E. M., Mueller, J. E., Yumashev, A. V., Kozachek, A. V., Prikhodko, A. N., & Safonova, E. E. (2019). Acquisition of entrepreneurial skills and competences: Curriculum development and evaluation for higher education. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 22(1), 1-12.
- Doan, X., & Phan, T. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intention: The case of Vietnamese. *Management Science Letters*, 10(8), 1787-1796.
- Edralin, D. (2016). *Entrepreneurship*. Quezon City: Vibal Group, Inc.
- Esubalew, A. A., & Raghurama, A. (2020). The mediating effect of entrepreneurs' competency on the relationship between Bank finance and performance of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 26(2), 87-95.
- Fayolle, A. (2018). Personal views on the future of entrepreneurship education. In Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781786432919.00013>
- Fotopoulos, G., & Storey, D. J. (2018). Public policies to enhance regional entrepreneurship: another programme failing to deliver? *Small Business Economics*, 53(1), 189–209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-0021-9>
- Frederick, H., O'connor, A., & Kuratko, D. (2016). *Entrepreneurship: Theory/Process/Practice*. (4th ed). Cengage learning Australia Pty Limited.
- Hahn, D., Minola, T., Bosio, G., & Cassia, L. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurship education on university students' entrepreneurial skills: a family embeddedness perspective. *Small Business Economics*, 55, 257-282.
- Iwu, C. G., Muresherwa, G., Nchu, R., & Eresia-Eke, C. E. (2020). University students' perception of entrepreneurship as a career option. *Academia*, (20-21), 177-201.
- Kuckertz, A., Kollmann, T., Krell, P., & Stöckmann, C. (2017). Understanding, differentiating, and measuring opportunity recognition and opportunity exploitation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
- Li, L., & Wu, D. (2019). Entrepreneurial education and students' entrepreneurial intention: does team cooperation matter?. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), 1-13.
- Liñán, Francisco. (2004). Intention-Based Models of Entrepreneurship Education. *Piccola Impresa / Small Business*. 2004. 11-35.
- Linton, G., & Klinton, M. (2019). University entrepreneurship education: a design thinking approach to learning. *Journal of innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 8(1), 1-11.
- Mahendra AM, Djatmika ET, Hermawan A. The effect of Entrepreneurship education on Entrepreneurial Intention Mediated by Motivation and Attitude among Managements Students, State university of Malang, Indonesia, *International Education Studies*. 2017; 10(9):61.
- Martínez-Rodríguez, I., Callejas-Albiñana, F. E., & Callejas-Albiñana, A. I. (2020). ECONOMIC AND SOCIO-CULTURAL DRIVERS OF NECESSITY AND OPPORTUNITY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEPENDING ON THE BUSINESS CYCLE PHASE. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 21(2), 373–394. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2020.11848>
- Mitchelmore, S., & Rowley, J. (2010). Entrepreneurial competencies: a literature review and development agenda. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 16(2), 92–111. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552551011026995>
- Nabi, G., Walmsley, A., Liñán, F., Akhtar, I., & Neame, C. (2016). Does

- entrepreneurship education in the first year of higher education develop entrepreneurial intentions? The role of learning and inspiration. *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(3), 452–467. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2016.1177716>
- Nazri, MA, Aroosha, H, Omar, NA (2016) Examination of factors affecting youths' entrepreneurial intention: a cross-sectional study. *Inf Manage Bus Rev* 8(5):14–24
- Neck, H. M., & Greene, P. G. (2011). Entrepreneurship education: known worlds and new frontiers. *Journal of small business management*, 49(1), 55-70.
- Peña, I., Guerrero, M., & González-Pernía, J. L. (2014). Global Entrepreneurship Monitor executive report. Informe GEM España.
- Petridou, E., Sarri, A., & Kyrgidou, L. P. (2009). Entrepreneurship education in higher educational institutions: the gender dimension. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 24(4), 286-309.
- Roxas, B. (2014). Effects of entrepreneurial knowledge on entrepreneurial intentions: a longitudinal study of selected South-east Asian business students. *Journal of Education and Work*, 27(4), 432-453.
- Ruskovaara, E., & Pihkala, T. (2015). Entrepreneurship education in schools: Empirical evidence on teacher's role. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(3), 236–249)
- Stoica, O., Roman, A., & Rusu, V. D. (2020). The nexus between entrepreneurship and economic growth: A comparative analysis on groups of countries. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1186.
- Taha, KA, Ramlan, SN, Noor, IM (2017) The factors affecting entrepreneurial intentions of university students in Malaysia. *IntJ Bus Technopreneurship* 7(2):189–202
- Tittel, A., & Terzidis, O. (2020). Entrepreneurial competences revised: developing a consolidated and categorized list of entrepreneurial competences. *Entrepreneurship Education*, 3(1), 1-35.
- Walter, S. G., & Block, J. H. (2016). Outcomes of entrepreneurship education: An institutional perspective. *Journal of Business venturing*, 31(2), 216-233
- Wang, S. M., Yueh, H. P., & Wen, P. C. (2019). How the new type of entrepreneurship education complements the traditional one in developing entrepreneurial competencies and intention. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 2048.
- Yi, G. (2020). From green entrepreneurial intentions to green entrepreneurial behaviors: the role of university entrepreneurial support and external institutional support. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 1-17.